

IPBES VA Chapter 4. Systematic review on motivational crowding by economic incentives in conservation policies / IPBES values assessment (4.1)

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the values assessment describes that *Chapter 4* should address values and valuation in relation to decision-making and policymaking at different levels and in different contexts. The chapter provides evidence on how conservation policies based on economic incentives affect the values at stake in the relevant decision-making processes. In this context a review of empirical studies focused on motivational crowding by economic incentives in conservation policies was conducted and is further described below.

Process overview

Protocol

Step 1. The paper by Rode et al. 2015 reviews the effects on motivation crowding of economic incentives in conservation policies. This paper and the 18 papers in the Rode et al. 2015 review constitute the first set of papers for the systematic review **(A)**.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** inclusion of the papers reviewed by Rode et al. (2015) and Rode et al. (2015) itself.
- **Sample extracted (A):** 19 (18 were the papers reviewed by Rode et al. 2015 + Rode et al. 2015 itself)
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - No
 - Full reference
 - Year of publication
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_4.1_01-2020_(A).csv

Step 2. The paper by Rode et al. 2015 also allowed the identification of keywords to perform a literature search, which focused on empirical work conducted on motivational crowding in the context of environmental policies, regardless the year in which they were conducted. The systematic search resulted in 60 papers, 8 of which were duplicated from the papers reviewed by Rode et al. 2015, and thus, were taken out. Consequently, the search resulted in 52 papers **(B)**.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic literature search of empirical studies on the effects of economic incentives in conservation policies on motivation crowding.
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Exact Search Date:** February 2020
- **Search terms:**

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY (
        (
            (motivation*) AND
            (crowd*) AND
            (environment* OR biodiversity OR ecolog* OR ecosystem OR forest
            OR "land use" OR agricultur* OR conservation*) AND
            (incentive* OR payment* OR polic* OR economic* OR compensate* OR
            mone* OR reward*) AND
            (experiment* OR survey* OR interview* "field stud*" OR "case
            stud*" OR workshop* or questionnaire*)) AND
        LANGUAGE: (English) AND
        DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article)
    )
)
```

- **Sample extracted:** 52 papers
- **Fields extracted (B):**
 - No
 - Full reference
 - Year of publication
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_4.1_02-2020_(B).csv

Step 3. Thirty-seven additional papers came from expert knowledge recommendations **(C)** (four of them were works in progress when suggestions arrived).

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Incorporation of additional literature through expert knowledge
- **Date:** This took place in three stages as recommendations came in over time.
- **Sample extracted:** 37 papers
- **Fields extracted (C):**
 - No
 - Full reference
 - Year of publication
- **Location and format of the data (C):** IPBES_VA_4.1_08-2021_(C).csv

Treatment applied: All papers from steps 1-3 were also checked against papers reviewed by Ezzine-de-Blas, Corbera and Laypere 2019. After screening, duplicated papers were left out. Thus, steps 1-3 resulted in a total of 108 papers ((A) + (B) + (C)).

A systematic search was conducted to identify studies focused on motivation crowding caused by the discourse emphasising instrumental values (specifically ecosystem services) that often goes along with conservation policies based on economic incentives.

Step 4. Rode et al. 2017 provided the starting point for this search (D).

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Inclusion of Rode et al. 2017, the papers cited by Rode et al. 2017 and the papers citing Rode et al. 2017.
- **Sample extracted:** 6 papers (including Rode et al. 2017)
- **Fields extracted (D):**
 - References short form - First author (Year)
 - Full reference
 - Year of publication
 - Abstract
- **Location and format of the data (D):** IPBES_VA_4.1_10-2020_(D).csv

Step 5. A systematic search was conducted, using three different search strings. This search had no time frame of empirical studies on motivation crowding caused by the discourse emphasising instrumental values (specifically ecosystem services) that often goes along with conservation policies based on economic incentives. The search resulted in 69 additional papers (E).

Details search string 1.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic literature database search.
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Exact search date:** 26 October 2020
- **Search terms:**

```
TS = (
  ■ TITLE-ABS-KEY
    (
      (motivation*) AND
      (crowd*) AND
      (environment* OR biodiversity OR ecolog* OR ecosystem OR
      forest OR "land use" OR agricultur* OR conservation*)
    )
  AND
```

```

(ecosystem services) AND (framing OR communication OR
arguments OR discourse OR cost-benefit analysis) AND
(experiment* OR survey* OR interview* OR field stud* OR
case stud* OR workshop* or questionnaire*)) AND
LANGUAGE: (English) AND
DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article)
)

```

- **Sample extracted search 1: 10 papers**

Details search string 2.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic literature database search.
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Exact search date:** 27 October 2020
- **Search terms:**

```

TS = (
  TITLE-ABS-KEY
    (
      (instrumental values) AND
      (environment* OR biodiversity OR ecolog* OR ecosystem OR
forest OR "land use" OR agricultur* OR conservation*) AND
(ecosystem services) AND (framing OR communication OR
arguments OR discourse OR cost-benefit analysis) AND
(experiment* OR survey* OR interview* OR field stud* OR case
stud* OR workshop* or questionnaire*)) AND
LANGUAGE: (English) AND
DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article)
    )
)

```

- **Sample extracted search 2: 11 papers**

Details search string 3.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic literature database search.
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Exact search date:** 27 October 2020
- **Search terms:**

```

TS = (
  TITLE-ABS-KEY
    (
      (motivation* OR crowd*) AND
      (environment* OR biodiversity OR ecolog* OR ecosystem OR
forest OR "land use" OR agricultur* OR conservation*) AND
(ecosystem services) AND (framing OR communication OR
arguments OR discourse OR cost-benefit analysis) AND
(experiment* OR survey* OR interview* OR field stud* OR case
stud* OR workshop* or questionnaire*)) AND
LANGUAGE: (English) AND
DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article)
    )
)

```

- **Sample extracted search 3: 48 papers**

Sample extracted for searches in step 4: 69 papers

- **Fields extracted (E):**
 - Publication type
 - Authors

- Article title
 - Source title
 - Abstract
 - Journal abbreviation
 - Journal ISO abbreviation
 - Publication year
 - Volume
 - Issue
 - Start page
 - End page
 - Article number
 - DOI
 - Date of export
- **Location and format of the data (E):** IPBES_VA_4.1_09-11-2020_(E).csv

Step 6. Additional paper recommendations were considered **(F)**.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Incorporation of additional literature through expert knowledge
- **Search language:** English
- **Sample extracted:** 2
- **Fields extracted (F):**
 - References short form - First author (Year)
 - Full reference
 - Year of publication
 - Abstract
- **Location and format of the data (F):** IPBES_VA_4.1_10-2020_(F).csv

Steps 4-6 resulted in a total of 77 papers **((D) + (E) + (F))**.

Treatment applied: To extract the final sample for analysis from steps 1 - 3, first, duplicates from different stages were screened out. Then, abstracts of all papers from steps 1-3 **((A), (B), (C))** were screened to identify the extent to which they satisfied criteria specified in **(R1)**. Final sample can be found in **(G)**.

- **Sample extracted:** 66 papers
- **Fields extracted (G):**
 - ID
 - Full reference
 - Year of publication
- **Location and format of the data (G):** IPBES_VA_4.1_19-08-2021_(G).csv

Note 1: During the analysis of the references in **(G)**, as we looked more closely and dug into the studies, we realised some studies (with no. 11, 16, 21, 40, 57 in **(G)**) were not suitable to find crowding effects. In other words, these studies did not meet the third inclusion criterion specified in R1; they were not “...suitable to establish empirical evidence of motivation crowding effects”. They were thus excluded

from the final analysis. The review papers (with no. 3, 13, 37, 47, 55 in **(G)**) were also excluded. These were used though to motivate the analysis and place the findings of the analysis within the broader relevant literature.

Treatment applied: To extract the final sample for analysis from steps 4 - 6, first, the relevance of the titles of all 77 papers was judged. Thirty-three of these were considered relevant **(H)**.

- **Sample extracted:** 33 papers
- **Fields extracted (H):**
 - ID
 - Full reference
 - Year of publication
- **Location and format of the data (H):** IPBES_VA_4.1_19-08-2021_(H).csv

Treatment applied: The abstracts of all 33 papers were screened to identify the extent to which they satisfied criteria **(R2)**. None of the papers in **(H)** met **(R2)** satisfactorily, although 17 of these partially did. We screened these papers more in detail expecting some could be used to prepare informed inferences and speculations on the impacts that particular framings and discourses may have on motivations for conservation. These are papers that e.g. study different framings and discourses on climate and environmental policy issues and their impacts on environmental behaviour and perceptions. After this more detailed screening it was decided to keep 7 of these 17 papers for the final analysis **(I)**. The other 10 papers were excluded.

- **Sample extracted:** 7 papers
- **Fields extracted (I):**
 - ID
 - Full reference
 - Year of publication
- **Location and format of the data (I):** IPBES_VA_4.1_19-08-2021_(I).csv

Note 2: during the screening of the 77 papers that resulted from steps 4 – 6 **((D) + (E) + (F))**, 6 papers fulfilling **(R1)** were identified. Of these, two papers had already been included in the list in **(G)** but the other four were included in the final analysis.

The systematic analysis of the retrieved papers identified the factors concerning policy design, process and context that influence the presence of crowding in, crowding out or no effects of incentive-based conservation policies on intrinsic motivations. Results of the analysis are presented in *section 4.3.4 Avoiding new value externalities through policy design* and in *annex 4.4*.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_4.1_01-2020_(A)	csv	4 KB	List of papers 19 papers (Rode et al. 2015 + 18 papers reviewed in that paper) - Step 1
B	IPBES_VA_4.1_02-2020_(B)	csv	11 KB	List of 52 papers resulting from the systematic literature search - Step 2
C	IPBES_VA_4.1_09-2020_(C)	csv	8 KB	List of 36 references assembled through expert recommendation - Step 3
D	IPBES_VA_4.1_10-2020_(D)	csv	9 KB	List of papers 7 papers (Rode et al. 2017 + 5 papers citing and cited in that paper) - Step 4
E	IPBES_VA_4.1_09-11-2020_(E)	csv	168 KB	List of 69 papers resulting from the systematic literature search - Step 5
F	IPBES_VA_4.1_10-2020_(F)	csv	4 KB	List of 2 papers assembled through expert recommendation - Step 6
G	IPBES_VA_4.1_19-08-2021_(G)	csv	14 KB	Final sample from steps 1 - 3
H	IPBES_VA_4.1_19-08-2021_(H)	csv	9 KB	First sample from steps 4 - 6
I	IPBES_VA_4.1_19-08-2021_(I)	csv	2 KB	Second and final sample of 7 relevant papers from steps 4 - 6
R1	IPBES_VA_4.1_03-2020_(R1)	txt	359 bytes	Rules for screening papers from steps 1 - 3
R2	IPBES_VA_4.1_03-2020_(R2)	txt	424 bytes	Rules for screening papers from steps 4 - 6